

Landscape analysis of national and international RDM initiatives

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Executive Summary

The Swiss Research Data Support Network (SRDSN) project, funded by the swissuniversities Programme Open Science I, aims to foster an inclusive community for research data support in Switzerland. Launched on January 1, 2024, the project involves 16 partners from Swiss higher education institutions and three domain-specific research infrastructures. A key focus of SRDSN is to establish best practices in research data management (RDM). The project comprises seven work packages, with Work Package 7 (WP7) specifically dedicated to international alignment, identifying key organizations, and promoting knowledge exchange.

This report summarizes the activities conducted within WP7 and outlines the outcomes achieved. It includes the methodology developed for a landscape analysis of RDM initiatives, a summary of key initiatives, an overview of initial collaborations established, and future plans.

The landscape analysis identified 26 international and 13 national RDM initiatives, which include initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The SRDSN aims to raise awareness of research data services, and promote and enhance the development of professionals involved in research data management support. Looking ahead, the SRDSN plans to establish an "International RDM Node" to engage with these and other initiatives and continue aligning Swiss RDM practices with international standards.

Introduction

The swissuniversities Programme Open Science I is dedicated to implementing the National Open Access (OA) Action Plan at Swiss Higher Education Institutions (HEI), as well as the National Open Research Data (ORD) Action Plan. The project "Swiss Research Data Support

Network (SRDSN)" was funded as part of the ORD Phase B of swissuniversities' Action Plan B5.3, which focuses on establishing a network for data stewardship.

The SRDSN project thus aimed to create a robust and inclusive research data support community in Switzerland. This network sought to facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the development of best practices among research data professionals from various disciplines and institutions, including libraries, IT services, core facilities, and research management offices. It built upon and expanded an existing grassroots research data support network in Switzerland that had been functioning informally for the past 4–5 years informally known as the Swiss Research Data Management (RDM) community. The SRDSN project was also closely aligned with the SwissDS-ENV project¹, another swissuniversities initiative aimed at creating a national network of data stewards, which in particular focused on the establishment of a Certificate of Advanced Studies in data stewardship.

At the early stages of the project submission, the SRDSN project brought together 13 partners from HEI in Switzerland (Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL), University of Teacher Education Vaud (HEPL), University of Teacher Education Bern (PHBER), University of Teacher Education Thurgau (PHTG), University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI), University of Basel (UNIBAS), University of Bern (UNIBE), University of Geneva (UNIGE), University of Lausanne (UNIL), University of Italian Switzerland (USI), University of Zurich (UZH), and Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) – as well as 3 domain-specific research infrastructures – Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH), Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS), and SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. The project received letters of support from 20 additional Swiss institutions. The SRDSN, a 12-month project, began its operational phase on January 1, 2024, and was granted a time extension at the end of that period, with a revised completion date of June 20, 2025. The SRDSN project was divided into seven work packages, and this report is a deliverable for Work Package (WP7), which focused on international alignment.

In the last fifteen years, several international institutions and initiatives, including Research Data Alliance (RDA²), Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI³), ELIXIR⁴, Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH⁵), and the European Open Sciences Cloud (EOSC) have actively promoted open research, Research Data Management (RDM), and data stewardship practices. In several European countries, such as Poland, Ireland, and the Netherlands⁶, national RDM and data stewardship networks are beginning to take shape. In Switzerland, SRDSN aims to bring together all professionals working in ORD, RDM, and data

¹ <https://wp.unil.ch/swissds-env/en/>, last visited on 16 June 2025

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>, last visited on 16 June 2025

³ <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>, last visited on 16 June 2025

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/>, last visited on 16 June 2025

⁵ <https://www.dariah.eu/>, last visited on 16 June 2025

⁶ <https://osf.io/9xjcd/wiki/home/>, last visited on 16 June 2025

stewardship across Switzerland. Notably, many SRDSN members and partners are also involved in international and European initiatives, ensuring alignment with broader developments and fostering opportunities for collaboration and engagement beyond national borders.

Within the SRDSN project, WP7 aimed to leverage these collaborations to strengthen connections within the SRDSN network and establish new ones. It sought to serve as a conduit between international and Swiss organisations, facilitating the exchange of experiences, knowledge, information, and best practices. By promoting the sharing of practices and experiences, SRDSN's and WP7's objective is to inspire Swiss researchers to actively participate, identify opportunities, and benefit from the offerings provided by these consortia.

WP 7 had three main tasks to achieve its objectives:

- 1) **Landscape analysis:** Identify key international RDM networks, organisations and initiatives across various scientific domains from which SRDSN partners could learn and ensure international compatibility, while also providing an overview of existing collaborations between Swiss higher education institutions and international partners.
- 2) **Initiate collaborations:** Establish contacts with key international institutions to exchange knowledge and experiences on open research, RDM, data management, and data stewardship to collect best practices.
- 3) **Define the future plans:** Create a continuation plan for the international engagements fostered by this network, in coordination with WP2 (Governance), ensuring that practices implemented in Switzerland are well aligned with international standards.

This report summarises the activities carried out for these three tasks and the outcomes achieved. It includes the methodology developed for conducting a landscape analysis of RDM initiatives, a summary of key initiatives, an overview of initial collaborations established, and plans for the future.

Landscape analysis

One of the primary objectives of the SRDSN, and consequently of WP7, was to identify key international organisations, initiatives, and institutions across various scientific domains for collaboration and knowledge exchange. This exercise was not meant to be exhaustive but rather to ensure that key or similar networks could be identified quickly, allowing some connections to be established within the timeframe of the funded project.

To map this landscape, we consulted all members of SRDSN and asked them to complete a table with key information about national and international initiatives they were familiar with or had learned about through their connections involved in RDM practices.

The landscape table included the following details:

1. Domain Focus: Whether the initiative is discipline-specific or generalist.

2. Scope: The geographical scope of the initiative, such as local, national, or international.
3. Type of Initiative: Information on funding sources (e.g., long-term or short-term funding, European/national, or others), structure, and any other type of formalism.
4. Size: The number of members involved in the initiative.
5. Maturity Level: The stage of development or maturity of the initiative.
6. Swiss Membership: Whether Swiss institutions or individuals are already members.
7. Membership Model: Whether the membership is institutional or individual, with or without fees, in-kind contributions, or any other membership fee model.
8. Services and Products: The types of services, training, tools, workflows, or other relevant products offered by the initiative.
9. Target Audience: Whether the initiative targets specific groups (e.g., data stewards, researchers, policy makers) or a broader audience (e.g., anyone interested in RDM).

The table was open for edition for two months, during which all SRDSN members were reminded to complete it via emails and during SRDSN meetings. At the end of this period, the table recorded 26 international and 13 national initiatives.

International initiatives

The initial list of international initiatives included 26 entries that were loosely related to RDM. Some entries were only marginally relevant to the scope of the SRDSN network. This was the case when: a) RDM was only a small part of the topics covered, b) the initiative functioned more as a repository than a network, and c) the entries were purely informational websites with a board of authors but lacked an active community.

Table 1 below provides a summary of the international initiatives that were thus deemed highly relevant for SRDSN and future interactions. This table includes the name and type of organisation, along with its domain and scope.

Table 1: International RDM initiatives

Organisation/Initiatives	Type
RDA Domain: General Scope: International	<p>The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is a global, community-driven initiative launched in 2013. Its mission is to build social and technical bridges that enable open sharing and reuse of data across technologies, disciplines, and countries. The RDA aims to address societal challenges by fostering collaboration among researchers, innovators, and technical experts through focused Working Groups, Interest Groups, and Communities of Practice. Membership is open to all. Its target audience is researchers, data professionals, policymakers and organisations in general.</p>
EOSC Domain: General Scope: International	<p>The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an initiative aimed at creating a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment for European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens. It enables the publication, discovery, and reuse of data, tools, and services for research, innovation, and education. EOSC promotes the FAIR principles to ensure reliable and efficient data management. EOSC aims to enhance research productivity, innovation, and trust in science by fostering collaboration and data sharing across disciplines and countries. Membership to the EOSC Association, the entity that governs EOSC, is open to European legal entities.</p>
UNESCO Global Open Science Partnership Domain: General Scope: International	<p>The UNESCO Global Open Science Partnership aims to make scientific knowledge more accessible, inclusive, and equitable. It supports the implementation of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, which sets international standards for open science practices. The partnership brings together diverse stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and private sector entities, to promote open science globally. There is an application procedure to become related or to become a partner.</p>
DataCite Domain: General Scope: international	<p>DataCite is an international consortium that aims to improve the accessibility, citation, and reuse of research data. Established in 2009, it provides Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for datasets, making them easily discoverable and citable. DataCite supports creating and managing metadata records, enhancing research workflows and promoting the FAIR principles.</p>

<p>LIBER Domain: General Scope: International</p>	<p>The Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche (LIBER) RDM Working Group aims to help libraries secure a critical role in the scholarly information infrastructure and recognize research data as valuable academic resources. It focuses on developing library services for FAIR research data, supporting data management during research projects, and linking data to publications. The group fosters knowledge exchange, identifies best practices, and collaborates with other RDM initiatives to enhance skills and infrastructure.</p>
<p>FORCE11 Domain: General Scope: International</p>	<p>FORCE11 is an international coalition of researchers, librarians, publishers, and research funders dedicated to improving scholarly communication and e-scholarship. Founded in 2011, it aims to enhance the research publishing system through various initiatives and working groups. Key activities include promoting the FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), the Research Resource Identification Initiative (RRID), and the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles (JDDCP). FORCE11 also organises an annual conference and the Scholarly Communications Institute to foster collaboration and innovation in research communication. Becoming a member of FORCE11 is straightforward and free of charge.</p>
<p>OpenAIRE Domain: General Scope: International (EU)</p>	<p>OpenAIRE is a European initiative that supports the Open Science movement by providing a comprehensive infrastructure for open scholarly communication. It connects research outputs from various data providers, making them accessible and reusable. OpenAIRE offers services to find, store, link, and analyse research data across all disciplines. It also promotes Open Science practices through training and support from a network of experts. Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program. The initiative offers a flexible membership structure that allows various organisations to join as full members or form partnerships. Members can participate in governance bodies, co-shape services and policies, and receive service discounts.</p>

<p>DARIAH Domain: Humanities and Arts Scope: International (EU)</p>	<p>The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) is a European initiative that enhances and supports digitally-enabled research and teaching in the arts and humanities. Established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2014, DARIAH connects researchers, institutions, and data across Europe. It provides tools, services, and training to facilitate digital resource creation, analysis, and preservation. DARIAH promotes best practices in data management and fosters collaboration through its network of Virtual Competency Centres, addressing challenges like data diversity and multimedia collections.</p>
<p>ELIXIR Domain: Life Sciences Scope: International (EU)</p>	<p>ELIXIR is a European intergovernmental organisation that unites life science resources from across Europe. Its mission is to coordinate and integrate bioinformatics resources to support life science research. ELIXIR connects national bioinformatics centres, data repositories, and research infrastructures, providing researchers access to a wide range of data, tools, and training. By fostering collaboration and standardising data management practices, ELIXIR enhances the efficiency and impact of life science research. ELIXIR has a very active RDM community working on developing training and promoting best practices in RDM.</p>
<p>PAGES Domain: Paleoclimate Scope: International</p>	<p>PAGES (Past Global Changes) is an international effort to coordinate and promote past global change research. It provides support for the gathering and synthesis of observations, reconstructions, and the modeling of climate, ecosystem, environmental and societal dynamics in the past. Data stewardship is one of its central objectives and it functions through working groups to support data stewardship practices.</p>
<p>LCRDM Domain: General Scope: National (NL)</p>	<p>The National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM) is a Dutch network of experts in RDM. It serves as a bridge between policy and practical solutions, addressing RDM topics that require a national approach. LCRDM brings together research support services, policymakers, IT specialists, and managers from various research institutes. It coordinates and facilitates collaboration among these stakeholders to tackle RDM challenges that are too large for individual institutions. The LCRDM also connects with other RDM groups in the Netherlands to enhance cooperation and innovation.</p>

<p>NFDI Domain: General Scope: National (DE)</p>	<p>The Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur (NFDI) is a German initiative to systematically manage, secure, and make research data accessible. Established in October 2020, NFDI coordinates efforts across more than 270 member institutions, including universities, research organisations, and other stakeholders. It operates through consortia that addresses both discipline-specific and cross-disciplinary data management challenges. NFDI promotes data as a common good for excellent research, enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of the German research system. It also ensures compliance with legal and ethical standards and fosters international collaboration.</p>
<p>DCC Domain: General Scope: National (UK)</p>	<p>The Digital Curation Centre (DCC) is a leading centre of expertise in digital information curation, focusing on building capacity, capability, and skills for research data management. Established in the UK, the DCC provides expert advice and practical assistance for storing, managing, protecting, and sharing digital research data. It offers a range of resources, including online tools, guidance, training, and consultancy services on policy development and data management planning. Furthermore, the DCC allows for a global membership and audience.</p>
<p>FRDN Domain: General Scope: National (BE)</p>	<p>The Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN) is a collaborative initiative involving 36 Flemish research organisations. It aims to motivate and enable researchers to exchange and reuse research data. The network supports the implementation of Open Science policies and connects with international initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).</p>
<p>ARDC Domain: General Scope: National (AUS)</p>	<p>The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) initiative provides Australian researchers with access to high-quality data, digital research infrastructure, and tools. Established in 2018, ARDC aims to enhance research capacity and innovation by enabling the creation, analysis, and retention of data assets. It supports various research activities through services like the Nectar Research Cloud and Research Data Australia.</p>

<p>DDOR CNRS Domain: General Scope: National (FR)</p>	<p>The Direction des Données Ouvertes de la Recherche (DDOR) at CNRS develops and implements policies for open research data. Established in 2020, DDOR aims to enhance the accessibility, management, and reuse of research data across various formats, including texts, documents, software, and publications. It supports the CNRS's Roadmap for Open Science and the Research Data Plan, ensuring alignment with national, European, and international initiatives. DDOR collaborates with CNRS's ten institutes to create a unified open science strategy and provides tools and services for data management, curation, and dissemination.</p>
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Swiss RDM initiatives

During the landscape analysis, the members of SRDSN identified several national initiatives and institutions that provide frameworks, policies, and support for researchers to manage their data according to international standards. These initiatives are essential for fostering collaboration, enhancing data reuse, and ensuring the long-term impact of research outputs, and several are already represented in the SRDSN. Table 2 summarises these national initiatives and highlights the key professionals leading these efforts in Switzerland. This table includes the name and type of organisation, along with its domain.

Table 2: National RDM initiatives

Organization	Type
<p>SNSF Domain: General</p>	<p>The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) is a science research support organisation mandated by the Swiss Federal Government. SNSF promotes ORD practices by requiring researchers to develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) for funded projects, encouraging the sharing of research data in public repositories, and supporting the development of strategies and infrastructure for research data management and data stewardship. The target audience consists of researchers and institutions.</p>

<p>CLARIN-CH Domain: Linguistics</p>	<p>CLARIN-CH is the national node of the pan-European linguistic research infrastructure Common Language Resources and Language Technology (CLARIN). It is a digital infrastructure that addresses the needs of researchers working with language data. One working group is concerned with managing sensitive and personal data and ethical and legal issues for linguistic data in Switzerland. CLARIN-CH is part of the national infrastructure roadmap and is coordinated by the CLARIN-CH consortium. The Linguistic Research Infrastructure (LiRI) acts as a technical centre providing data and services. Membership is open to all Swiss Higher Education Institutions. The target audience is mainly researchers.</p>
<p>DARIAH-CH Domain: Humanities</p>	<p>DARIAH-CH is the national node of the pan-European Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH). It is a digital infrastructure that addresses the needs of researchers who work with humanities data. DARIAH has a dedicated RDM working group (WG) which works on specific topics, often in collaboration with other DARIAH working groups. Today, the RDM WG is concerned with multilingualism and managing textual corpora in under-resourced languages. DARIAH-CH is part of the national infrastructure roadmap and is coordinated by the Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH). Membership is open to all Swiss Higher Education Institutions. The target audience consists of researchers and data stewards.</p>
<p>EnhanceR Domain: Science IT</p>	<p>EnhanceR is a network for research IT expertise with the legal form of an association. It offers the open RDM.swiss service, which provides researchers with an RDM solution according to the FAIR principles. Membership is open to legal persons, corporate bodies and institutions with an interest in the purpose of the association. The target audience consists of researchers and institutions.</p>
<p>SCNAT Domain: General</p>	<p>The Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences (SCNAT) are involved in shaping the national Open Research Data Strategy and its implementation. It also intends to contribute to developing competencies in ORD research practices and respective framework conditions. The target audience is researchers.</p>
<p>FORS Domain: Social Sciences</p>	<p>Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS) is a research data infrastructure for the social sciences. It provides training, consulting and a repository service for social science scholars. FORS is a foundation and part of the national research infrastructure roadmap. The target audience consists of researchers and data stewards.</p>

<p>SCTO Domain: Biomedical</p>	<p>Swiss Clinical Trial Organisation (SCTO) is a research infrastructure that provides tools and services to clinical research professionals. It offers courses on good clinical practice. SCTO is part of the national research infrastructure roadmap. The target audience consists of researchers.</p>
<p>SDSC Domain: General</p>	<p>Swiss Data Science Center (SDSC) is a research data infrastructure whose mission is to accelerate the use of data science and machine learning techniques within the ETH Domain academic disciplines. SDSC is part of the national research infrastructure roadmap. The target audience is researchers.</p>
<p>Swiss Geosciences Domain: Geosciences</p>	<p>Swiss Geosciences is a platform for the academic disciplines of geosciences. It is aimed at being an interface between research, administration, politics and the public.</p>
<p>SIB Domain: Life Sciences</p>	<p>SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics is the national node of ELIXIR, the pan-European Life Sciences Research Infrastructure. It is a foundation that offers services, resources, expertise, and training to researchers working with life sciences and clinical data. SIB is in the national research infrastructure roadmap. Several SIB groups assist researchers in data management planning, annotation, and standardization, as well as by developing tools and platforms for long-term data storage and sharing. Its target audience includes researchers in bioinformatics and data stewards.</p>
<p>DaSCH Domain: Humanities</p>	<p>Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) is a research data infrastructure for the social sciences. It provides training, consulting and a repository service for humanities scholars. DaSCH is an association, and membership in the association is open to all Higher Education Institutions. It is part of the national research infrastructure roadmap. The target audience consists of researchers and data stewards.</p>
<p>SPHN Domain: Biomedical</p>	<p>Swiss Personal Health Network (SPHN) is a research infrastructure enabling the nationwide use of health data for research. It builds on existing data resources and infrastructures across Switzerland. SPHN provides documents and guidelines relevant to research data management tailored to its target audience, which consists of researchers and data stewards.</p>

<p>SwissRN Domain: General</p>	<p>Swiss Reproducibility Network (SwissRN) is a consortium which aims to foster a broad interdisciplinary dialogue to improve reproducibility and replicability in all empirical disciplines. To achieve this goal, SwissRN provides appropriate training activities and best practices guidelines. Membership is open for institutions committed to supporting and implementing the aims of SwissRN. The target audience consists of researchers and institutions.</p>
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Short-term outcomes: engagement during the project

The landscape analysis identified 26 international initiatives, prompting a discussion within the network about the best approach for alignment within the project timeframe. We considered two options: maintaining a minimal approach, as in the initial analysis, which would not require shortlisting or prioritizing, or adopting a more comprehensive strategy. The latter would involve in-depth research and understanding of each initiative, necessitating the selection of the most critical ones for the SRDSN community.

After consulting with project WP leaders, the WP7 members decided to follow the minimal approach. This involved leveraging existing connections for informal collaboration and prioritizing organizations with pre-existing ties to facilitate easier introductions. This method would allow for quicker exchanges, including mutual presentations of the SRDSN project and the international organizations.

In line with this decision, WP7 members have invited representatives from RDA and DARIAH—specifically, a Swiss representative—to present at the SRDSN biannual meeting scheduled for 7 November 2024. Wolmar Nyberg from Uppsala University and the National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden (NBIS) delivered a presentation titled "Introducing the Research Data Alliance (RDA): Leveraging Global Data Communities in Regional Initiatives"⁷, and Rita Gautschy from DaSCH introduced DARIAH.

As of now, this exchange has led to a boosted awareness within the SRDSN about the RDA framework, its mandate, and available forums. WP7 has also identified some concrete next steps for potential collaboration with RDA. For example, WP7 and Wolmar Nyberg envision potential exchange visits for SRDSN members to Sweden. Additionally, the alignments between the SRDSN community and the DARIAH framework have become more evident.

Moving forward, SRDSN will continue this effort by reaching out to other international initiatives listed in Table 1, encouraging their key members to engage with SRDSN events. By inviting these experts to present their activities and share their experiences, we aim to create a vibrant platform for knowledge exchange. Additionally, we will ensure that these international collaborators are well-informed about our network's ongoing and future

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14042880>, last visited on 16 June 2025.

activities, thereby strengthening our global connections and enhancing the impact of our initiatives in the long run.

Mid- and long-term plans for national and international engagements

SRDSN aims to raise awareness and facilitate knowledge exchange regarding research data services, support, infrastructures, and best practices within Swiss institutions. Additionally, it promotes the professional development of ORD professionals, research data managers and data stewards across the national landscape. The objective is to allow any RDM professional working at a Swiss HEI to join the network, even if their HEI has not signed the network's Memorandum of Understanding. We will actively promote membership and ensure these individuals know the network's existence.

While individuals from institutions outside of Swiss HEI, such as private companies, governmental institutions (e.g., SEFRI), museums, and private galleries, cannot become members of SRDSN, they are still welcome to participate in SRDSN events, present their activities, and stay informed about the network's activities. They may also be invited to collaborate within SRDSN's topic-specific nodes. Our goal is to be inclusive by sharing knowledge and experiences broadly.

For SRDSN, engaging with national and international RDM initiatives and aligning best practices across countries and regions will be key. By learning from others, we can save efforts within the SRDSN, continuously improve, and stay at the forefront of open research practices.

To promote these connections and mutual influence between Switzerland and the global community, the SRDNS plans to establish an "International RDM Node". In this Node, SRDSN members will be appointed as "liaison officers" for specific projects, and be responsible for engaging with international communities and regularly providing updates to the node members.

The activities of these liaison officers may include:

- Reviewing processes and practices to gain insights into ongoing international activities and share those with SRDSN members.
- Monitoring new initiatives and organisations that are of interest to establish new collaborations.
- Coordinating, streamlining and promoting long-term partnerships between national and international efforts.